

Research paper

Hypoplastic model with an inner memory surface for sand under cyclic loading

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ABSTRACT

We propose a hypoplastic model for granular soil using the memory surface notion to consider the stress history. This paper aims to resolve the limitations of the hypoplastic model that are rooted in the neglected memory impacts. First, we make use of the intergranular strain concept in conjunction with a reference hypoplastic model to present a simple model accounting for cyclic loading. Further, by integrating the memory concept into the hypoplastic model using intergranular strain, we present a new hypoplastic model that can recall the strain and stress history. The memory surface is derived from the constitutive model employing a definition of dissipation energy. The loading criterion based on the dissipation surface improves the model's performance in predicting cyclic loading. Finally, the performance of our models is compared based on laboratory tests.

1. Introduction

Recently, the hypoplastic models have attracted much interest in numerous studies to describe the behavior of soil (Wu and Niemunis, 1997; Wu, 1998, 2000; Bauer et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2018). The complex soil behavior under cyclic loading still poses a major challenge for constitutive models, which are needed in assessing the serviceability of some geotechnical engineering problems such as road pavement, offshore structures, and machine foundations to name a few (McVay and Taesiri, 1985; Klinkvort and Hededal, 2013; Fuentes et al., 2020). Hypoplastic models are developed as a function of stress and stretching tensors lacking the details of loading history (Wu and Kolymbas, 1990; Wu and Bauer, 1994; Bauer, 1996; von Wolfersdorff, 1996; Wu et al., 1996; Wu and Niemunis, 1996). In spite of the fairly well performance of the model in predicting monotonic loading, it tends to produce identical stress–strain curves for primary loading and reloading in a loading cycle (Bauer and Wu, 1993; Niemunis and Herle, 1997; Fuentes et al., 2012). The model's shortcomings can be seen in the unrealistic prediction of volume change and stiffness in cyclic drained tests and the prediction of stiffness and pore water in the cyclic undrained tests. Experimental studies show that material behavior undergoes changes during cyclic loading, which is attributed to the formation of new force chains, alterations in fabric, and compaction. The loading history and its impact on material behavior can evidently play a crucial role in improving the model performance for cyclic loading (Tatsuoka and Ishihara, 1974; Dafalias and Popov, 1975; Niemunis and Herle, 1997; Pradhan et al., 1989;

Wichtmann, 2005; Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a; O'Sullivan and Cui, 2009; Chow et al., 2015; Corti and Diambra, 2017).

Some efforts have been made to enhance the performance of hypoplastic models for cyclic loading by incorporating the memory effect, which refers to the impact of loading history on material behavior (Fuentes et al., 2012; Fuentes and Triantafyllidis, 2015; Fuentes et al., 2020; Liao and Yang, 2021, 2022b,a). The concept of intergranular strain, which takes into account the material's recent deformation, was proposed by Niemunis and Herle in 1997 (Niemunis and Herle, 1997). In this framework, a rapid change in the strain path results in varying stiffness values depending on the direction of the strain rate. While this capability significantly improves predictions for small strain amplitudes, it reveals limitations when applied to cyclic loading with varying ranges of strain amplitudes. The limitations of the model are displayed in the form of overshooting and ratcheting, which can be attributed to the linear range assumption with a fixed size and the consideration of only the recent deformation history (Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015a; Bode et al., 2020; Duque et al., 2021). The accumulation of overshooting and ratcheting over a number of cycles can lead to the unrealistic prediction of stiffness and volume change (Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015a; Bode et al., 2020). A hypoplastic model with a loading surface has been proposed by Fuentes et al. (2012) which aims to consider the memory effect in the reloading stage. This model borrowed the notion of bounding surface and loading surface plasticity to formulate the hardening functions (Imam et al.,

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2002; Dafalias, 1981, 1986). Although the model can consider the memory effects, it cannot produce an acceptable stiffness increase in reloading (Fuentes and Triantafyllidis, 2015). Following the intergranular strain concept, the ISA model has been proposed by Fuentes and Triantafyllidis (2015) with a yield surface and bounding surface using the plasticity notions (Dafalias, 1981, 1986). In this model, the yield surface and bounding surface are proposed in the intergranular strain space with constant sizes. The ISA model benefits from a yielding and bounding surface in strain space that enables the model to consider the recent deformation of the material (Fuentes and Triantafyllidis, 2015; Poblete et al., 2016; Fuentes et al., 2020). Still, the predictions of the ISA model for triaxial cyclic drained test and oedometer cyclic loading tests display ratcheting (see ISA predictions in Wichtmann et al., 2019). The limitation of the ISA model may be explained by consistent dimensions of the surfaces that affect the alterations in the stiffness. Furthermore, restricting the analysis to solely the most recent portion of the loading history could provide additional clarification for ratcheting.

Experimental studies on granular soil subjected to non-monotonic loading indicate that the soil behavior is dependent on the loading history in stress space. The observed outcomes suggest the inclusion of additional features in constitutive models to account for the loading history in the stress space (Wichtmann, 2005; Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a; Chow et al., 2015; Corti et al., 2015). The evolution of fabric under cyclic loading leads to a stable structure in a soil element. Consequently, the granular soil with the loading experience shows a higher stiffness in comparison to the soil under the primary loading condition. The stress paths beneath the maximum stress experienced by soil have no considerable influence on the particle arrangement (Chow et al., 2015). In the elastoplastic macro-element model presented by Chow et al. (2015), the observed increase in sand stiffness subjected to cyclic loading due to changes in soil density and the fabric is explained by utilizing an expandable memory surface. An additional memory surface is incorporated by Corti and Diambra (2017) in an elastoplastic constitutive model, representing the relatively stable fabric associated with the historic stress states that the soil has already experienced. The memory surface has been utilized by Jafarzadeh et al. (2008) in modeling the anisotropy of granular soil in the true triaxial tests (Chow et al., 2015; Corti et al., 2015). The term memory surface was incorporated into the Sanisand constitutive model by Liu et al. (2019) as a means of capturing the cyclic response of the material in relation to its micro-mechanical fabric. In this study, the concept of a memory surface within the stress space is introduced, with the objective of integrating the fabric-related influence of all stresses experienced by the material throughout its loading history. To ensure that the entire loading history is taken into account, the memory surface encompasses all the stress states experienced by the material.

This paper presents a new approach to hypoplastic modeling for cyclic loading, combining the concepts of the memory surface and intergranular strain. The simple hypoplastic model recommended by Wu et al. (1996) is adopted as a reference model. Initially, a primary model is proposed, which relies exclusively on the intergranular strain concept. The primary model offers a simplified formulation while still providing acceptable predictions in comparison to similar models. Subsequently, the paper introduces the new hypoplastic model, which incorporates the memory surface concept, a loading criterion, and the intergranular strain concept. The memory surface and the loading criteria are defined using the dissipation surface. The dissipation surface is a graphical surface utilized in stress space, whereby all stress states on this surface have the same amount of dissipation energy. Eventually, to show the advancements made in incorporating the memory surface concept, the performance of the models in predicting the cyclic loading tests is compared.

The notations and conventions in this article are as follows. The second-order tensors are represented in the bold font (e.g. \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{T}), and the fourth-order tensors are represented in the calligraphic font (e.g. \mathcal{L}).

The unit symmetric fourth-order tensor \mathcal{I} is defined as $I_{ijkl} = 1/2(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk})$ where δ_{ij} is Kronecker delta. The double dot product is denoted with the colon “:” and is defined as $\mathbf{A}:\mathbf{B} = A_{ij}B_{ij}$. The dyadic product of two tensors is denoted with no sign and is defined as $\mathbf{AB} = A_{ij}B_{kl}$. The Euclidean norm of a second-order tensor denoted with $\|\square\|$ and defined as $\|\mathbf{A}\| = \sqrt{A_{ij}A_{ij}}$ where $\|\mathbf{A}\|$ is stated simply as the norm of \mathbf{A} in this article. The normalization of a tensor is denoted with an arrow sign on top of the tensor ($\vec{\square}$) and defined as $\vec{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A}/\|\mathbf{A}\|$ where in the article $\vec{\mathbf{A}}$ is stated simply as the direction of \mathbf{A} .

2. The reference hypoplastic model

The general form of the hypoplastic constitutive equation can be formulated as a tensor-valued function \mathbf{H} , that

$$\dot{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{T}, \mathbf{D}, e) \quad (1)$$

The Jaumann stress rate ($\dot{\mathbf{T}}$) is a function of the Cauchy stress tensor (\mathbf{T}), stretching tensor (\mathbf{D}), and void ratio (e). The tensor-valued function \mathbf{H} should be homogeneous in \mathbf{T} , and positively homogeneous of the first degree in \mathbf{D} . According to Wu and Bauer (1994) and Wu et al. (1996), the function \mathbf{H} with the help of representation theorem for two symmetric tensors (Wang, 1970) and a density function (I_e) can be written as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{T}} = \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{T}) : \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{T})\|\mathbf{D}\|I_e \quad (2)$$

The presented model (Eq. (2)) embodies two parts that function linear and nonlinear in stretching tensor. The modification to be recommended interacts with the linear and nonlinear phrases and this approach can also be employed for the models with the same feature. In Einstein notation, the tensors \mathcal{L} and \mathbf{N} can be in brief derived as:

$$L_{ijkl} = c_1 T_{nn} \delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + c_2 T_{ij} T_{kl} / T_{nn}, \quad (3)$$

$$N_{ij} = (c_3 T_{ik} T_{kj} + c_4 T_{ij} T_{ij}^*) / T_{nn}, \quad (4)$$

where $c_i (i = 1, \dots, 4)$ are dimensionless constant of the hypoplastic model, and \mathbf{T}^* is defined as $T_{ij}^* = T_{ij} - T_{nn} \delta_{ij} / 3$. The density function I_e is appended to the preliminary version of the model (Wu and Bauer, 1994) to consider the effect of volume change and critical state in predictions.

$$I_e = (q_1 + q_2 \exp(q_3 T_{nn}) - 1) \frac{e_{cr} - e}{e_{cr} - e_{min}} + 1, \quad (5)$$

where e_{min} and $q_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ are constant parameters and e_{cr} is the critical state void ratio corresponding to stress state (\mathbf{T}). With variations in the parameter I_e , the model's stiffness can exhibit both hardening and softening behavior, leading to changes in volume (Wu et al., 1996).

3. IS Hypoplastic model

The intergranular strain concept is employed in hypoplastic models to include a linear response after an abrupt shift in strain path (Niemunis and Herle, 1997). Implementation of this concept has the potential to enhance the model's performance with regard to small strain amplitudes, subsequent to a change in loading conditions. Nevertheless, the current model still encounters difficulties in effectively capturing the stiffness improvement during cyclic loading with different strain amplitude ranges, leading to the occurrence of ratcheting and overshooting (Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a; Bode et al., 2020; Fuentes and Triantafyllidis, 2015; Fuentes et al., 2020). In this section, we propose an intergranular strain (IS) hypoplastic model on the basis of the hypoplastic reference model in Section 2. According to pioneer work of the Niemunis and Herle (1997), the rate of intergranular strain $\dot{\mathbf{Y}}$ is defined as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{Y}} = \begin{cases} \left[\mathcal{I} - \vec{\mathbf{Y}} \vec{\mathbf{Y}} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{Y}\|}{R} \right)^\chi \right] : \mathbf{D} & \vec{\mathbf{Y}} : \mathbf{D} > 0 \\ \mathbf{D} & \vec{\mathbf{Y}} : \mathbf{D} \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where χ is a constant parameter, R is the maximum value of the intergranular strain, and \mathbf{Y} is the intergranular strain tensor. In case $\|\mathbf{Y}\| = 0$, $\vec{\mathbf{Y}}$ considered as $\mathbf{0}$ which is a zero tensor of second order.

3.1. Mathematical formulation of the IS Hypoplastic model

The reference model consists of linear and nonlinear parts. With the help of the intergranular strain, we recommend two scalar functions f_L and f_N for linear and nonlinear parts respectively:

$$\dot{\mathbf{T}} = f_L \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{T}) : \mathbf{D} + f_N \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{T}) \|\mathbf{D}\| I_e, \quad (7)$$

where f_L and f_N are defined as:

$$f_L = m + 0.5(1 - m)(1 + \beta)\rho_i, \quad (8)$$

$$f_N = \langle \beta \rangle \rho_i, \quad (9)$$

where m is the constant parameter and it indicates the maximum linear stiffness multiplier. The signs $\langle \cdot \rangle$ are Macaulay brackets that means $\langle x \rangle = x$ if $x \geq 0$, and $\langle x \rangle = 0$ if $x < 0$. For simplification, we decreased the number of multiplier parameters to one. The term β implies the deviation of the $\bar{\mathbf{Y}}$ from stretching tensor, and is defined as $\beta = \bar{\mathbf{Y}} : \bar{\mathbf{D}}$. In other words, β is the cosine value of the angle between the stretching tensor and intergranular strain. The term ρ_i is the normalized value of \mathbf{Y} by the maximum value of the intergranular strain:

$$\rho_i = (\|\mathbf{Y}\|/R)^{\alpha_1}, \quad (10)$$

where α_1 is a constant parameter. After a sharp change in strain path, β takes a negative value that helps to deactivate temporarily the nonlinear part. The function f_L takes the maximum value of m in cases $\beta = -1$ and $\rho_i = 0$. The output of both functions f_L and f_N gradually turns to 1 when $\beta = 1$ and $\rho_i = 1$ at the same time. In this article, the primary value of the δ is considered as $\bar{\mathbf{R}}\bar{\mathbf{D}}$ which means the model function in the same manner as the reference model in primary loading.

4. MS-IS Hypoplastic model

The memory surface concept has been taken into account to recall the stress states that the material has experienced. Memory surface can be explained as a concept to consider the fabric changes due to the earlier loading (Corti et al., 2016; Corti and Diambra, 2017; Corti, 2016; Chow et al., 2015). With the help of memory surface and loading conditions, we can resolve the ratcheting and overshooting in the IS-Hypoplastic model's prediction for cyclic loading. In the following, the memory surface (MS) in conjunction with the intergranular strain (IS) is utilized in introducing the MS-IS hypoplastic model.

4.1. Dissipation surface

Dissipation energy is part of mechanical energy that transforms into irrecoverable energy and produces entropy. With the assumption that an element receives uniform stress and homogeneous straining, and the plastic-free energy is constant; we have (Huang et al., 1981; Yang et al., 2018; Collins and Houlsby, 1997; Wu and Niemunis, 1996):

$$\Phi = \mathbf{T} : \mathbf{D}^p, \quad (11)$$

where the Φ is the rate of dissipation energy per unit volume and \mathbf{D}^p is the plastic strain rate. Since there is no clear definition for the elastic and plastic increments in the hypoplastic model, we use the simple definition recommended by Wu and Niemunis (1996) for plastic strain increment in the hypoplastic model. The irrecoverable strain in a small closed loop of the stress cycle ($\mathbf{T} \rightarrow \mathbf{T} + \dot{\mathbf{T}}dt \rightarrow \mathbf{T}$) is considered as plastic strain. With the help of definition and Eq. (2) it can be concluded that (Wu and Niemunis, 1996):

$$\mathbf{D}^p = k\mathbf{B}, \quad (12)$$

where k is a scalar function and \mathbf{B} is the flow rule. In this work, the term flow rule tends to be used to refer to the strain rate that $\mathbf{D} \in \mathcal{K} = \{\mathbf{D} | \dot{\mathbf{T}} = 0\}$. To put it simply, within the failure surface, there exists a \mathbf{D} for each stress state \mathbf{T} which makes stress increment disappear ($\dot{\mathbf{T}} = 0$).

Fig. 1. Dissipation surface in stress space with using Eq. (15) for Karlsruhe medium sand (Wu and Niemunis, 1996).

Failure surface refers to a surface in the stress space that represents the set of stresses that lead to the exhaustion of shear strength and failure in granular materials (Wu and Niemunis, 1996). According to definition and using Eq. (2), the flow rule (\mathbf{B}) can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{B} = -\mathcal{L}^{-1} : \mathbf{N} I_e \quad (13)$$

The flow rule is a function of stress (\mathbf{T}) and void ratio (e). In the following, for simplification, we consider the flow rule as a function of stress that simplifies Eq. (13) to $\mathbf{B} = -\mathcal{L}^{-1} : \mathbf{N}$. The direction of the flow rule is important in our model and simplifying it by using I_e as a scalar function does not alter its direction. Moreover, this simplification leads to the flow rule being solely dependent on stress, which in turn simplifies the subsequent equations, as seen in the work of other researchers (Wu and Niemunis, 1996). With using the maximum rate of internal entropy (Ziegler and Wehrli, 1987), the scalar function for the maximum value of Φ can be defined as (Wu and Niemunis, 1996):

$$k = \frac{-2}{\xi - \mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B}}, \quad (14)$$

where ξ is a constant parameter. To avoid cases $\mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B} = 1$, we consider ξ a constant greater than one. By substituting Eqs. (12) and (14) into Eq. (11) we have:

$$\Phi = \frac{-2\mathbf{T} : \mathbf{B}}{\xi - \mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B}} \quad (15)$$

For a constant value of Φ we can plot a teardrop-shaped dissipation surface in stress space (see Fig. 1). The dissipation surface with a greater energy rate encompasses surfaces with smaller energy rates. In the following sections, it will be illustrated how the dissipation surface and Φ help to define loading criteria and recall the stress states that the material has experienced. Since the relative values of the current and preceding Φ are utilized in the formulation of the model, the value of the ξ more or less does not influence the predictions. The constant ξ is set as an arbitrary real number greater than one (e.g. 1.5) that helps to create a teardrop-shaped dissipation surface.

4.2. Mathematical formulation of the MS-IS Hypoplastic model

The MS-IS Hypoplastic model defines the memory surface by employing the maximum dissipation energy rate per unit volume (Φ_m) that the granular soil has experienced. The memory surface is the dissipation surface with Φ_m dissipation energy rate per unit volume. As explained earlier, for a stress point \mathbf{T} within the failure surface

Fig. 2. The visualization of the idea: (a) visualization of loading, unloading, and reloading stress path (b) definition of Γ and its sign in a stress path.

there exists a dissipation surface with Φ dissipation energy rate per unit volume. In stress space, an increase in Φ leads to stretching the surface out of the center where it encloses all previous smaller dissipation surfaces and experienced stress states. Fig. 2(a) present a visualization of loading ($a_1 \rightarrow b_1$), unloading ($b_1 \rightarrow c_1$) and reloading ($c_1 \rightarrow d_1$) stress paths. The size of the dissipation surface by loading stretches from DS_a surface to DS_b then shrinks to DS_c and again expands to DS_a . If we assume that soil at point a_1 is under a virgin loading condition, the stress state lies on the memory surface in $a_1 \rightarrow b_1$ stress path. With the initiation of unloading, DS_b surface remains the memory surface for stress path $b_1 \rightarrow c_1$ and also for the reloading stress path $c_1 \rightarrow d_1$ with maximum experienced Φ . As explained, in our model, the memory surface does not shrink and may expand to encompass all the experienced stress states.

The MS-IS model assumes that the soil is virgin, but the initialization of the memory surface for over-consolidated sand can be achieved by calculating the maximum past effective stress through isotropic and oedometer tests. This enables the initialization of the memory surface using the maximum past effective stress and Eq. (15), even if the actual loading history is unknown.

4.2.1. Loading criterion

With the help of the dissipation surface, flow rule, and the intergranular strain concept, we can define a standard to assume a loading criterion (Tatsuoka and Ishihara, 1974). In this work, the loading criterion is expressed as:

$$\lambda := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{unloading} & \Gamma < 0 \wedge \beta < 0 \\ 1 & \text{loading} & \Gamma \geq 0 \wedge \beta < 0 \\ \lambda_{old} & & \beta \geq 0, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where λ is the loading variable and takes 0 and 1 values to consider the loading and unloading situation in the model's formulation. Γ is described as:

$$\Gamma = \dot{\mathbf{T}} : \mathbf{B} \quad (17)$$

Whereas \mathbf{B} is perpendicular to the dissipation surface, the sign of Γ explains the direction of the $\dot{\mathbf{T}}$ according to the dissipation surface. For instance, in Fig. 2(b), the value of the Γ at the stress state \mathbf{T}_i takes positive and negative values for stress increments toward the outside ($\dot{\mathbf{T}}_1$) and inside ($\dot{\mathbf{T}}_2$) the dissipation surface respectively. However, Γ independently cannot be enough loading criterion. To illustrate the point consider stress path $a_2 \rightarrow b_2 \rightarrow c_2$, in which the sign of Γ is negative at the beginning of unloading, but it changes at point b_2 while the stress path is not changed. The sign of Γ can change in the middle of a loading condition without any sharp change in strain or stress path. To overcome such a vacancy, we consider β in addition to Γ in the loading criterion. Consequently, λ changes at the very beginning of a loading process that $\beta < 0$ and keeps the value subsequently.

4.2.2. Multiplier functions

The memory surface and loading criterion in conjunction with the intergranular strain concept are utilized to define new multiplier functions f'_L and f'_N . In like manner, the MS-IS hypoplastic model can be derived as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{T}} = f'_L \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{T}) : \mathbf{D} + f'_N \mathbf{N}(\mathbf{T}) \|\mathbf{D}\| I_e, \quad (18)$$

where functions f'_L and f'_N are linear and nonlinear multiplier respectively and defined as:

$$f'_L = m + 0.5(1 - m)(1 + \beta)\rho_i^{(1-\lambda)}\rho_m^\lambda, \quad (19)$$

$$f'_N = ((\beta)\rho_i)^{(1-\lambda)}\rho_m^\lambda \quad (20)$$

In Eqs. (18) to (20), under the unloading condition that $\lambda = 0$, both MS-IS and IS Hypoplastic models function in the same manner (see Section 3). It is assumed that the model under the unloading condition is independent of the memory surface. Apart from the advantage of the intergranular strain concept in the definition of loading criteria, it helps to provide a linear stiffness in the early stages of unloading. Under the loading condition that $\lambda = 1$, the effect of the memory surface with the ρ_m appears. The variable ρ_m is the relative dissipation energy rate concerning a reference surface and the memory surface:

$$\rho_m = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\Phi - \Phi_0}{\Phi_m - \Phi_0} \right)^n & \Phi_m \neq \Phi_0 \\ 1 & \Phi_m = \Phi_0, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where Φ , Φ_m and Φ_0 are the dissipation energy rate per unit volume of current dissipation surface, memory surface and the reference surface respectively. The reference surface is used to refer to the dissipation surface at the initiation of a loading/unloading process. In the model, Φ_0 can be recorded efficiently under the condition that β is less than zero. For instance in Fig. 2(a), during the stress paths $a_1 \rightarrow b_1$, $b_1 \rightarrow c_1$ and $c_1 \rightarrow d_1$ the reference surfaces are DS_a , DS_b and DS_c respectively. For the definition of n we have:

$$n = \alpha_2 \left(\frac{\Phi_0}{\Phi_m} \right), \quad (22)$$

where α_2 is a constant parameter of the model. The Eq. (22) considers the interspace between the memory surface and the reference surface in the formulation of the model. In the predictions of the cyclic loading oedometer and isotropic compression tests with small and large domains of stress/strain cycles, n benefits by deterring ratcheting and overshooting.

5. Performance of the models

For validation, we use the quality experimental results of Karlsruhe fine sand with different boundary and control conditions (Wichtmann

Table 1
IS and MS-IS Hypoplastic model parameters for Karlsruhe sand.

Model constant	Symbol	Value	Units
Hypoplastic	c_1	-71.9	[-]
	c_2	-633.5	[-]
	c_3	-595.0	[-]
	c_4	444.1	[-]
Density function	e_{min}	0.40	[-]
	q_1	1.0	[-]
	q_2	-0.31	[-]
	q_3	1.0×10^{-4}	[kPa]
Critical state	p_1	1.054	[-]
	p_2	4.0×10^6	[kPa]
	p_3	0.27	[-]
Intergranular strain	R	1.1×10^{-4}	[-]
	χ	0.35	[-]
Multiplier functions	m	5.0	[-]
	α_1	9.0	[-]
	α_2	9.0	[-]
Dissipation surface	ξ	2.0	[-]

and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a; Wichtmann, 2018). The constant parameters of both models (IS and MS-IS) for Karlsruhe fine sand are presented in Table 1. The critical state line recommended by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b) for Karlsruhe fine sand is employed for prediction. The critical void ratio (e_{cr}) corresponding to the stress **T** is expressed as :

$$e_{cr} = p_1 \cdot \exp \left[-(T_{nm}/p_2)^{p_3} \right], \quad (23)$$

where p_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) are the constants and parameters of the critical state line.

The conventional triaxial tests are employed to calibrate the constant parameters of the reference hypoplastic model and density function. In Fig. 3, the results of drained triaxial compression tests with different relative densities are compared with the predictions of the model. The predictions of the model show acceptable agreement in predicting the steady state, strain softening, and shearing dilatancy. In Fig. 3(a), the initial stiffness is found to be overestimated for the loose specimens, while it demonstrates improvement for the denser specimens (Figs. 3(b) and 3(c)). Reducing the initial stiffness could improve the model's performance for loose specimens, but this would come at the expense of a significant underestimation of the stress-strain curve for denser specimens. Additionally, it is worth noting that while the reference model may appear to produce almost identical strain curves for loose specimens in Fig. 3(d) with varying initial mean effective stress, the influence of changes in the mean effective stress can be observed in the case of medium-dense and dense specimens in Figs. 3(e) and 3(f).

The parameters of the IS hypoplastic model are delicately determined using the calibrated reference model. For more details about the calibration of the reference hypoplastic model and the constant parameters related to the intergranular strain concept, see Wu and Bauer (1994), Wu et al. (1996) and Niemunis and Herle (1997). The constant α_2 is the parameter of the MS-IS hypoplastic model and the last parameter needs to be determined. With Isotropic cyclic compression and oedometer tests, α_2 can be efficiently calibrated where the predictions for the small and large domains of stress or strain cycles should not overshoot or ratchet.

5.1. Predictions of triaxial cyclic drained tests

The hypoplastic reference model predicts acceptably the behavior of the granular soil in primary loading and unloading conditions. The reference model is defined as a function of the stress state and stretching tensor. Therefore, it produces similar predictions for primary loading and reloading which is not supported by experiments (Tatsuoka and

Ishihara, 1974; Dafalias and Popov, 1975; Pradhan et al., 1989; Bode et al., 2020; Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a). Relatively, the IS hypoplastic model with the help of the intergranular strain concept can solve the problem by increasing the model's stiffness after a sharp change in strain path. In Figs. 4(a) to 4(c), three triaxial cyclic drained tests are compared with the predictions of the IS hypoplastic model. Excluding an adequate increase in the stiffness at the early steps of the reloading, predictions show ratcheting in the loops of unloading and reloading. The comparison of the IS prediction in Figs. 4(a) to 4(c) shows that the decrease of the axial strain increment ($\Delta \epsilon_1$) between the cycles can also lead to more unrealistic results due to ratcheting. Comparing the prediction of models in Fig. 4 indicates that the memory concept can improve the hypoplastic model performance in the triaxial cyclic drained condition. Using a memory surface in the MS-IS model helps to recall the stress history and predict the loading cycles relatively well. In Figs. 4(d) to 4(f), the predicted stiffness increases sharply at the beginning of the reloading and it decreases gradually by approaching the memory surface. The memory impact deactivates when the stress state reaches the memory surface.

5.2. Predictions of the oedometer cyclic loading tests

The Fig. 5 shows experimental data and the models' predictions for three oedometer cyclic loading tests with different void ratios. The intergranular strain concept provides a practical approach to increasing the model's stiffness with a change in loading condition. In the IS model, the increase of the stiffness cannot continue to the unloading starting point which leads to predicting excessive volume change (see Fig. 5(b)). Ratcheting also can be noticed in Figs. 6(b) and 6(e) for two oedometer cyclic loading tests that use IS model. The accumulation of ratcheting causes a considerable difference between the predictions and the experimental results. As in Figs. 5(c), 6(c) and 6(f) presented, using the memory concept can improve the predictions for oedometer cyclic loading tests significantly. The MS-IS model transforms from partly linear to nonlinear behavior when the stress path returns to the unloading point and closes the loading cycle quite well.

5.3. Predictions of the isotropic cyclic loading tests

In Fig. 7, two isotropic cyclic loading tests are compared with the IS and MS-IS hypoplastic models' predictions. Although the ratcheting in the predictions of the IS model for one cycle is negligible, the accumulation of the ratcheting after 10 cycles of unloading and reloading brings about considerable differences between predicted void ratios and IS model's predictions. The MS-IS model with the record of the stress states that the material has experienced can keep the linear multiplier function greater than one, and the nonlinear multiplier function less than one until the initial unloading point to solve the ratcheting.

In Figs. 8(a) and 8(d), two isotropic cyclic loading tests with small loading amplitude are presented. The specimens are loaded and unloaded isotropically 200 kPa four times with a constant positive 100 kPa stress increment between the cycles. Additionally, at the stress point $p = 800$ kPa, the specimens are loaded and unloaded isotropically 200 kPa four times but with a constant negative 100 kPa stress increment between the cycles (the specimens unloaded 300 kPa and reloaded 200 kPa). In Fig. 8, The experimental data contains two types of cyclic loading: first, the state of the material reaches the virgin loading line and continues loading; second, the state of the material does not reach the primary loading line while the next cycle starts. Such experimentation can flawlessly illustrate the vision of the memory concept in granular soils. In Figs. 8(b) and 8(e), from the onset of the cyclic loading, the IS model predicts almost a constant linear stiffness which can be seen as a straight line cutting the primary loading line (see also predictions in Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015a). In this case, the IS model determines the condition as linear during the entire cyclic loading. In Figs. 8(c) and 8(f), thanks to the presence of a loading criterion and different approaches for loading and unloading in the MS-IS model, it can perfectly predict the cyclic isotropic compression tests with a small stress amplitude.

Fig. 3. Predictions and experimental data of the conventional triaxial drained test: (a, d) loose, (b, e) medium dense, and (c, f) dense samples. The simple solid lines are the predictions of the model. Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

Fig. 4. Prediction and experimental data of the triaxial cyclic drained tests with a constant axial strain increment between cycles: (a, d) $p_0 = 100$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.701$ [-], $\Delta\epsilon_1 = 2\%$; (b, e) $p_0 = 100$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.820$ [-], $\Delta\epsilon_1 = 6\%$; (c, f) $p_0 = 100$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.821$ [-], $\Delta\epsilon_1 = 12\%$. The predictions of the IS hypoplastic model and MS-IS hypoplastic model are compared with the experimental results in (a, b, c) and (d, e, f) respectively. Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

5.4. Predictions of the triaxial undrained cyclic loading tests

In the undrained non-monotonic loading conditions, the performance of the hypoplastic model can be improved effectively using the intergranular strain concept. The intergranular strain concept enhances the predictions in terms of excess pore water pressure and the number of cycles before failure (Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a). In Fig. 9, we see the performance of the IS and MS-IS model in predicting a triaxial cyclic undrained test with initial anisotropic stress. As in Section 4.2.2 stated, the IS and MS-IS model in the unloading criterion

that $\lambda = 0$ functions analogously. At the beginning of the loading steps the stress increment direction is toward the inside of the dissipation surface ($\Gamma < 0$). Therefore, λ is assessed as zero in the entire cyclic loading, and both models perform similarly. Likewise, in Fig. 10, the IS and MS-IS hypoplastic models predict the exact behavior for a cyclic undrained test with constant deviatoric stress amplitude. The comparison of the predictions and experiments shows the ability of the model in producing the number of cycles and butterfly-shaped zone in stress space. In Fig. 11, the MS-IS model discerns between unloading and reloading which brings about a slight difference between the IS and

Fig. 5. Predictions and experimental data of three Oedometer cyclic loading tests with different initial void ratios: (a) experimental data, (b) the IS hypoplastic model's prediction, and (c) MS-IS hypoplastic model's prediction.

Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

Fig. 6. Predictions and experimental data of two cyclic Oedometer tests: (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model.

Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

MS-IS model's prediction. In general, the predictions of the MS-IS model is not much different from the IS model under undrained condition. It can be articulated that the MS-IS model has kept the strengths of the IS model in predicting undrained tests.

6. Conclusion

This study was designed to instruct a practical granular soil hypoplastic model for cyclic loading. The introductory model (IS hypoplastic) is recommended to append the intergranular strain concept to the reference model. In addition to the simplicity of our IS model, it has a reasonable performance equivalent to the models with the identical approach (Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis, 2015b,a; Wichtmann et al., 2019).

Further, the memory surface concept is utilized to consider the stress history which is an absent aspect of the granular soil in hypoplastic modeling. The MS-IS hypoplastic model utilized the memory surface concept in conjunction with the intergranular strain. The loading criterion is defined with the use of the flow rule, dissipation surface, and intergranular strain tensor. The memory impact appears during

reloading and is deactivated during unloading condition (Fuentes et al., 2012; Fuentes and Triantafyllidis, 2015). A comparison of the two models indicates the ability of the MS-IS model in solving ratcheting and overshooting in triaxial drained, isotropic compression, and oedometer cyclic loading tests. The IS model cannot present a precise prediction for the drained cyclic loading tests with small domains of stress or strain (for instance see Fig. 8). The MS-IS model uses a loading criterion and different approaches for loading and unloading conditions that help to predict correctly the cyclic loading tests with small domains of stress or strain.

The MS-IS model improves the IS model with the memory concept, as well as saving the strength of the IS model, particularly in undrained situations. The IS model demonstrates reasonable predictions for the triaxial cyclic undrained test before failure. In general, there is a slight difference between the IS and MS-IS models' predictions for triaxial cyclic undrained tests. In the MS-IS model, there are cases in which the criterion is assessed as unloading during the entire cyclic undrained test. In such conditions, both models produce similar predictions because the models function in the same manner in unloading. Despite the convincing performance of the MS-IS model, it still needs advancement

Fig. 7. Predictions and experimental data of two cyclic isotropic compression tests: (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model.

Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

Fig. 8. Predictions and experimental data of two cyclic isotropic compression tests: (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model.

Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

Fig. 9. Predictions and experimental data of triaxial cyclic undrained test with constant axial strain amplitude and initial anisotropic stress ($p_0 = 50$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.833$, $\eta_0 = 0.75$, $\epsilon_1^{amp} = 6 \times 10^{-4}$): (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model. Source: Experiments by [Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis \(2015b,a\)](#).

Fig. 10. Predictions and experimental data of triaxial cyclic undrained test with constant deviatoric stress amplitude ($p_0 = 200$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.842$, $q^{amp} = 40$ kPa): (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model. Source: Experiments by [Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis \(2015b,a\)](#).

Fig. 11. Predictions and experimental data of triaxial cyclic undrained test with initial anisotropic stress and a constant deviatoric stress amplitude ($p_0 = 300$ kPa, $e_0 = 0.812$, $\eta_0 = 0.5$, $q^{amp} = 120$ kPa): (a, d) experimental results, (b, e) the predictions of IS hypoplastic model, and (c, f) the predictions of the MS-IS hypoplastic model. Source: Experiments by Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis (2015b,a).

in the unloading prediction of the triaxial cyclic drained tests and post-failure prediction of the triaxial cyclic undrained tests.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammad-Javad Alipour: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Figures, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Wei Wu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The two authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article

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